

Research

Educational Level and Occupation as Predictors of Children's Performance in Bauchi State

Hamisu Idi^{1*}, Sagir A. Mahmud², Muhammad Mubarak Muhammad³, Abubakar Adamu⁴
^{1,2,3,4} Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Federal Polytechnic, Bauchi, Nigeria

***Corresponding Author**

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Abstract: *This study seeks to investigate selected family background factors that influence students' academic achievement in senior secondary school in Bauchi state. To guide the study, four hypotheses were formulated and tested. The design for the study is comparative design. The sample for this study was 400 students randomly selected on the basis of 50% male and 50% female each from 253 schools in Bauchi state. The selection of schools is based on the three senatorial districts in the state on the proportion of 2: 6 : 2 (central, south and north) respectively. Questionnaire on the family background and influence was designed and tested. The data collected was analyzed using correlation, regression analysis and t – test statistic. The findings reveal that parental involvement, educational level, family size and socio – economic status significantly influence students' performance. Student whose parents assisted in their academic work performed better than those who did not, while occupation had no effect on performance. However, unequal attention was given to male and female students. Furthermore, private schools performed more than public. It is concluded that parental educational background and availability of study facilities at home greatly influenced academic performance. Consequently, parents should endeavor to be involved in the academic activities of their children.*

Keywords: *Performance, Parental factors, family size, influence.*

Introduction

The home is the first place of learning for the child. The quality of home environment goes a long way in determining the eventual personality and achievement of the child. Psychologists have classified the factors that affect learning into two broad categories namely, nature and nurture. These two categories play complementary roles. Nature determines the level of

intelligence and inherited abilities of the child while nurture helps to maximize these innate abilities. According to Ekinne (2002; p.28), nurture involves the home, school, environment and peer groups to which the learner belongs. Nyakor (2008) suggested that the home environmental variables could be manipulated to enhance students' academic performance.

The position of educational opportunities for children in this present economic depression has generated a lot of problems such as high cost of school fees, cost of educational materials and other facilities. As a result of insufficient fund and economic instability, the continued investment in the education industry is now assuming a socio – economic status dimension. The home environment still serves as a strong indicator to the aspiration and academic achievement of the younger generation. Because most children's sound education are now confronted with a lot of increasing difficulties as a result of home climate of which the socio – economic background has a strong hold.

In a study of the educational achievement of institutions of learning, educated and uneducated homes in Western Nigeria, Ogunlade (1995; p. 438) opined that children of illiterate homes perform worse than their counterparts from the educated homes. Students from this home also study and concentrate more in the class than the former. Nyakor (2011) confirmed that there is significant relationship between educational background and academic performance, while Hoover and Sandler (2005) supported the observations on the two types of family background,(the elite and traditional household), that the family setup affects the child degree of verbal behaviors', instructional attitudes, and communication, which in turn affects the child's academic in several courses. Miedel and Reynold (2000), on the child study attributed academic performance at school to the parents' attitudes and their level of educational attainment.

In a family where both (the parents)are educated, their children always take good care of their academic activities. Such parents know the importance of getting educational materials for their children (Fan and Chen, 2001; p. 11) and may go through their children's exercise books after school, or even employ private teacher to teach them after school. By so doing, their academic performance will improve; whereas in the case of illiterate family, the need to supervise the children's exercise books is absent, hence their children's will experience low academic performance in school. Educated parents may also have library at home, stocked with novels,

encyclopedia and other educational books and educational audio visual tapes. When children make use of these materials, it will enhance their intellect.

Some parents/ sponsors do not make any enquiry about the academic performance of their children by asking for the result of their children at the end of any academic session. Students from such homes are usually carefree. According to Community Development, Sound Education, Good Health and Social Life (2013), the community often has a marked influence on the students' motivation for learning and on his ability to profit from his influences at school. Parent's engagement has a positive impact on student's academic achievement, behavior in school, attitude about the school and work. But what is becoming clear that it is not the school that failed, it's partnership that failed with schools taking on the responsibility that family, communities and religious institutions once assumed. The community often has a marked influence on students' motivation for learning and on his ability to gain from his influence at home.

Many poor parents have been unable to meet the costs of training their children and so opt not to enroll their children in schools. The increased level of poverty makes parents unable to feed their children properly and provide education. Children whose parents cannot afford the cost of instructional materials, school uniforms, tuition fees and activity fees, tend to go to school irregularly and in the long run drop out of school (Government of Kenya, 2000).

A Family's socio-economic status correlates with channelized surveillance by the parents and involvement in their child's academics. That status is based on family's income (Epstein, 1995; p. 705). After passing secondary high socio-economic status, often are more successful in school certificate examination students from higher preparing their young children for school because of the economic status. Some families are more likely to attend high school than access they enjoy to harness resources responsible to lower-income students. Those in elite educational centers promote and support young children's development, learn independent thinking and decision-making skills (Olatoye, 2008; p. 13).

The value that different families attach to education could affect the child's attitude to school and eventually affect his/her motivation for success in school work. Muola (2010) stated that "the urge to achieve varies from one individual to the other. For some, the need for achievement is very high while for others, it is very low. He adds that achievement motivation is learnt through

the socialization process. Those who have high achievers as their role models in their early life experience would develop a high need for achievements while those who have low achievers as their role models will hardly develop the need for achievement". The family is obviously a major socializing agent and therefore important in determining the child's motivation to achieve success. The motive to excel in academic work is an activating force, a drive or an urge to achieve good results and recognition which accounts to good academic performance (Epstein, 1995; p. 711).

Illiteracy of parents could have a negative effect on the academic performance of their children. Children whose parents are illiterates have been seen to lack home encouragement. This implies that as some illiterate parents refuse to provide their children with needed textbooks, they are discouraging them from learning. However, David (2007; p. 29) stated that textbooks aid studies after normal school teaching. Students from illiterate parents lack assistance because of parents' illiteracy and ignorance as such parents fail to motivate, reinforce, give reward or punish their children on their academic performance which might force them not to be serious in learning. Literate parents on the other hand have interest in their children's academic performance. They struggle to provide them with needed materials and give adequate encouragement. Having known the importance of education, they draw reading time-table for their children, arrange for part-time teachers to teach their children, check their workbooks from time to time and also take care of their children's provision and needs, especially educational needs. These are very important in determining the academic performance of children.

Problem Statement/ Justification

Home is the first school for a child where he/she is taught the basic norms and values by the parents before the child leaves for formal education. Contrary to the opinion that learning and reading begins in school, the first foundation for the child begins at home. A good and conducive home environment with adequate learning facilities would help to boost the intellectual and academic capability of the child.

Education has a long lasting impact on one's life. The acquisition of knowledge and skills and all other things that are worthwhile are transmitted to a person through formal and informal education which determines one's potential in future. The motivation of any intelligent child

towards learning is accelerated by the positive influence of his/her environment while others are negatively affected in terms of their non-stimulating home environment.

At the end of every instructional period in school comes examination. Over the years, the society has been recording a persistent increase in the rate of poor performance in various school examinations such as the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) and if this trend is not nip in the bud, it will have grave repercussion on the lives of these students, their parents and the society at large.

Researches have shown that the blame for poor performance has been as the result of neglect and carefree attitude exhibited towards academic work by students and parents. Well educated parents would always have good attitudes towards education and provide learning materials such as television, instructional video tapes, novels, books and journals that could facilitate the learning process.

Objectives of the Study

1. To test if parental involvement, family size, education level and occupation will significantly influence students' achievement (performance).
2. To determine whether there is significant difference in parental involvement in students' achievement in private and public schools.
3. To determine whether there is significant difference in parental involvement in students' academic work based on gender.
4. To test whether there is significant difference in academic achievement (performance) in public and private schools.

Research Hypotheses

1. Parental involvement, family size, education level and occupation will not significantly influence students' performance
2. There is no significant difference in parental involvement in students' academic achievement in public and private schools.
3. There is no significant difference in parental involvement in students' academic achievement based on gender.
4. There is no significant difference in students' academic achievement in public and private schools.

Literature Review

Some parents and families are able to be involved in many ways of their children's educational aspirations while others may only have time for one or two activities. Whatever the level of involvement, consistency matters a lot as it would make an important difference in the child's life (Utah Education Association, 2008). The cultivation of strong family- school linkages is increasingly and widely viewed as an essential component of strategies to improve students' educational outcomes. However, research conducted by Epstein (1995; p. 708) and Gianzero (2001) reported that family practices of involvement are of more important than family background variables in determining whether and how students' progress and success in school because no one is more than parents in sending the signals that reading and education matter and that school work is not a form of drudgery but a ticket to a better life. By encouraging their children and assisting on homework, parents set example for their child, which is powerful and positive (Gianzero, 2001). In a survey conducted by Conway and Houtenwille (2008), they found out that parental involvement has a strong positive effect on student achievement. Some parents and families are able to be involved in many ways; others may only have time for one or two activities.

Many researchers acknowledge a strong direct relationship between Socio- Economic Status (SES) and academic achievement, they also claim that motivated families, regardless of their SES, can and do help their children improve school performance through several types of involvement. Research documenting the effects of parental involvement at home and in school concludes that differences in the achievement levels of working class and middle-class children is more explained by the nature of child-parent and parent-school interactions than by characteristics of SES (Flouri and Buchanman, 2004; p. 149; Conway, 2008).Ezewu and Okoye (1981) found that educated parents who most often fall into high or middle-economic class families tend to show more concern over their children's poor performance at school either by teaching them in those subjects in whom they performed poorly or they appoint lesson teachers to further coach them. Ezewu (1990) said that children from high socio-economic status families are likely to improve on their academic achievement even if they have been performing poorly before because they can be provided with the incentive to do better.

The family could be regarded as an essential agent of education (Morsbach and Printz, 2006; p. 192). Furthermore, the families influence child rearing practices and socio – economic level which appear to affect vocational development. Nyakor (2010; p. 340) says” it is the family that makes the child to be identified by the society, culture, religious or social class. The family continues to exercise a strong influence over the child’s life and academic performance in the school. Just as families differ vastly in terms of significance, and in social order, some have more prestige, money, wider experience and knowledge of how to operate within the social or school environment. That is to say socio – economic status matters a lot.

Family size is another factor that determines the academic performance of the students. Researchers acknowledge a strong direct relationship between family size and academic achievement, they also claim that motivated families, regardless of their SES, can and do help their children improve school performance through several types of involvement. Research documenting the effects of parental involvement at home and in school concludes that differences in the achievement levels depends on the number of children and SES of the family.

Berkeley Parent Network (2009) asserted that private schools vary widely and the level of parental involvement varies from one private school to the other. What is important is for parents to choose private school that has characteristics that match what they are looking for as a family. Parents pay for the cost of educating their children in private schools and tend to be more involved in dictating what the school offer than parents whose children are attending public schools (Agbatogun, 2009).

Mcmillian (2000) also reported that parental involvement in public schools is a strong determinant of school performance as measured by students’ scores in achievement tests. Thus, parents influence the educational process of their children. The importance of parental involvement can- not be over emphasized. To make this completely meaningful, both parents should be involved. Garg et al, (2007; p. 1018) found that youths from single-parent families reported lower educational aspiration than those from two-parent families. Another issue is whether parents are more involved in their female child’s educational progress than their male child’. Olatoye and Ogunkola (2008; p. 36) reported that there is no significant difference between how parents are involved in their male and female child’s academic progress.

Research shows that parental involvement in their children’s learning positively affect the child’s academic performance (Fan and Chen, 2001; p. 8). Fennstein and Symons (1999; p. 314) agreed

with this and concluded that it works in both private and public secondary schools. Melhinsh et al, (2001) discovered that parental involvement in children's learning lead to higher academic achievement, greater cognitive competence, greater problem solving skills, greater school enjoyment, better school attendance and fewer behavioral problems at school.

Henderson and Berla (1997) and Gianzero (2001) asserted that when schools work together with families to support learning, children tend to succeed not just in school, but throughout life. No doubt the recognition of the importance of parental involvement in school and academic achievement is affirmed by the United States government through a declaration in a federal Legislation enacted in 1994. The declaration tagged The Goals 2000: Educate America Act, states that "By the year 2000, every school will promote partnerships that will increase parental involvement and participation in the social, emotional and academic growth of the children". Utah Education Association (2008) asserted that when parents are involved in their children's education at home, they do better in schools. The cultivation of strong family- school linkages is increasingly and widely viewed as an essential component of strategies to improve students' educational outcomes.

Research design

The descriptive and comparative study was employed in carrying out this study. This design is considered most appropriate in this content because it allows the researcher to make comparisons between two or more groups, thus identifying the relationship, influence and the difference between the variables. The design also accommodates generalization of the findings from the whole population from which only a representative portion was actually studied.

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

The target population for the study comprises of Senior Secondary School Students in Bauchi state from both public and private schools. However, indices from The Ministry of Education reveal that the total number of students in public and private schools were 106,123 as at 2014/2015 Annual School Census Figures, comprising 89,912 and 16,211 for public and private respectively.

The sample size 'n' is:

1. For Schools: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} = \frac{690}{1+690(0.05)^2} = 253.211$
2. For Students: $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} = \frac{106,123}{1+106,123(0.05)^2} = 398.4979$

That is to say, about 400 students were extracted from 250 schools in the state. The selection was based on the ratio proportion of the number of schools available in each of the senatorial districts in the state, i.e. 2 : 6 : 2, representing central, south and north senatorial districts respectively (both public and private). Questionnaires were administered on the basis of simple random sampling procedure. As a comparative study, public and private schools were sampled on the basis of 50% each for both genders. The analysis of the data was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) computer software, version 20. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, standard error and inferential analysis like correlation, regression and T-test, will be used to analyze the data. Tables will be used to present the analyzed data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. *H₀: Parental involvement, family size, education level and occupation will not significantly influence students' performance*

a. Influence on parental involvement:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.790 ^a	.624	.621	.298

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	56.183	3	18.728	210.444	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.817	380	.089		
	Total	90.000	383			

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.721	.048		15.138	.000

Learning Materials	.462	.033	.968	14.214	.000
Assignment or Home work	.167	.040	.372	4.196	.000
Report/ Score Sheet?	-.228	.034	-.607	-6.706	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Current Performance.

The result from the analysis shows that there exists a strong relationship between the learning materials supplied by parents to their children, assisting them with assignment as well as regular checking of their score sheet with $R = 0.79$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was found to be .624. This shows that 62.4% of the total variation is explained by the changes in the independent variables (learning materials, assignment and score sheet); in other word providing learning materials, guiding with assignment and regular checking of score sheet by parents explained student's performance with 62.4%.

From the multiple regression model, $Y = 0.721 + 0.462X_1 + 0.167X_2 + 0.228X_3$, where X_1 is learning materials, X_2 is assignment and X_3 is report/ score sheet. This shows that these variables have significant effect on the students' performance as their beta weights (0.462, 0.167 and 0.228 respectively) with their varied 't' values which are all statistically significant as their various P-values are all less than 0.05. The slope in the model which is about 72.1% shows that there are other factors that influence the students' performance apart from those under study.

b. Influence on family size

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.885 ^a	.782	.781	.227

a. Predictors: (Constant), No. of Children, No. of Wives, Family Type

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	70.420	3	23.473	455.549	.000 ^b
	Residual	19.580	380	.052		
	Total	90.000	383			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance.

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.

	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.356	.041		8.629	.000
1 Family Type	.639	.043	.647	14.869	.000
No. of wives	.015	.022	.026	.661	.509
No. of children	.026	.003	.284	8.767	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance.

There exists a strong relationship between the family type, number of wives and the number of children with $R = 0.885$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is found to be 0.728. This shows that 72.8% of the total variation was explained by the changes in the independent variables (family type, number of wives and number of children); in other words, the family size has a significant effect and explains child's performance with 72.8%.

The regression equation is $Y = 0.356 + 0.639X_1 + 0.015X_2 + 0.026X_3$, where X_1 is the family type, X_2 is number of wives and X_3 is number of children in the house. Family size have a significant effect on the students' performance as their beta weights (0.639, 0.015 and 0.026 respectively) with their varied 't' values which are all significant as their various P- values are all less than 0.05.

c. Influence on education level & occupation

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.673 ^a	.453	.450	.359

a. Predictors: (Constant), Parents' Occupation, Parents' Education Level.

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	40.776	2	20.388	157.807	.000 ^b
	Residual	49.224	381	.129		
	Total	90.000	383			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance.

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	.994	.060		16.479	.000
	Parents' Education Level.	-.041	.016	-.103	-2.646	.008
	Parents' Occupation	.475	.027	.690	17.699	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance.

There is a strong relationship between the parents' education level and their occupation with $R = 0.673$. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is found to be 0.453. This shows that 45.3% of the total variation is explained by the changes in the independent variables (parents' education level and occupation); in other words, the parents' education level and their occupation explains child's performance with 45.3%.

The regression equation is $Y = 0.994 - 0.041X_1 + 0.475X_2$, where X_1 is the parents' education level and X_2 is occupation. Occupation has a significant effect on the students' performance considering its beta weight (0.475: $P = 0.000$ value which is less than 0.05). However, parents' education level has a negative effect in the model which shows its insignificance. In other words parental education level does not have strong influence on students' performance.

Therefore, parental involvement in their children's educational upbringing and their socio – economic well-being (parent's education level, occupation and family size) influence their children's performance, hence null hypothesis is rejected.

2. H_0 : There is no significant difference in the parental involvement in their children's educational upbringing from public and private schools.

Group Statistics

	School Category	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Learning Materials	Public	192	1.43	.893	.064
	Private	192	2.80	.565	.041
Assignment or	Public	192	1.86	.686	.050

Homework	Private	192	3.65	.518	.037
Report/ Score Sheet	Public	192	1.19	.730	.053
	Private	192	3.47	.433	.031

Variable	T	d.f	Sig.
Learning Materials	18.022	382	.000
Assignment or Homework	28.798	382	.000
Report/ Score Sheet	37.146	382	.000

The critical value of the test statistic corresponding to the degree of freedom, $t_{\frac{\alpha}{2}, 382} = t_{\frac{0.01}{2}, 382} = t_{0.05, 382} = 1.645$. The calculated values (18.022, 28.798 and 37.146) are all greater than the critical value; hence the null hypothesis is rejected and therefore concludes that parental involvement in children's educational upbringing differs significantly in average between public and private schools. It is observed that respondents who enrolled their children in private schools provides them with learning materials (mean = 2.80), assist them with assignment or homework (mean = 3.65) and check their report/ score sheet on a regular basis (mean = 3.47) more than that of their public counterpart with learning materials (mean = 1.43), assist them with assignment (mean = 1.86) and been checking their report/ score sheet on a regular basis (1.19).

3. *H₀: There is no significant difference in the parental involvement in their children's educational upbringing for male and female students.*

Group Statistics

	Respondents' Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Learning Materials	Male	192	1.59	.807	.058
	Female	192	2.64	.934	.067
Assignment or Homework	Male	192	2.44	1.091	.079
	Female	192	3.06	.980	.071
Report/ Score	Male	192	1.97	1.092	.079

Sheet	Female	192	2.69	1.367	.099
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Variable	T	d.f	Sig.
Learning Materials	-11.698	382	.000
Assignment or Homework	-5.857	382	.000
Report/ Score Sheet	-5.734	382	.000

The critical value of the test statistic corresponding to the degree of freedom 382, $t_{\frac{\alpha}{2},382} = t_{\frac{0.01}{2},382} = t_{0.05,382} = 1.645$. The calculated values (-11.698, -5.857 and -5.734) are all greater than the critical value in absolute, hence the null hypothesis is rejected and therefore concludes that parental involvement in children's educational upbringing differs significantly in average between male and female students. It is observed that the female child is given more attention than the male child in terms of providing learning materials, assignment or homework and checking of report sheet with mean of (2.64, 3.06 and 2.69) respectively while the male child has an average of (1.59, 2.44 and 1.97) respectively.

4. *H₀: There is no significant difference in the parental involvement in their children's educational upbringing for male and female students.*

Group Statistics

	School Category	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Performance	Public	192	1.45	.399	.029
	Private	192	1.80	.499	.036

Variable	t	d.f	Sig.
Performance	7.681	382	.000

The critical value of the test statistic corresponding to the degree of freedom 382, $t_{\frac{\alpha}{2},382} = t_{\frac{0.01}{2},382} = t_{0.005,382} = 1.645$. The calculated value is 7.681, which is greater than the critical value in, hence the null hypothesis is rejected and therefore concluded that the overall performance differ significantly between public and private secondary schools in average. It is also observed this as their varied average, where private schools exceeds public schools ($1.80 > 1.45$), despite the fact that the difference is not much, and as such it is considered as they are all within a pass.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Socioeconomic status statistically and significantly influence children's performance suggesting that pupils whose parents are of higher socio-economic status, higher educational level and both parents are significantly involved in their children's school work and enhance them to perform better academically. Furthermore, the best predictors of children's academic performance are parental involvement, educational level, family size and socio-economic status.

Furthermore, parents who belong to low socio – economic group find it difficult to assist their children with their academic goals. It is the contrary with the high socio – economic group. Also, both group of students had (almost) the same grade of pass. It was observed that students from small family size are well provided with learning materials which aids academic work because such families are more financially equipped to sponsor their children's education at all level. Parents' educational level significantly influence and has relationship with educational attainment of children as children from more educated group tend to do better and have higher aspirations and education plans.

A review by Henderson and Berla (1997) of parental involvement concluded that the most accurate predictor of students' achievement in school are family size, income or social status, as well as the extent to which families are able to create a home environment that supports learning; communicate high and reasonable expectations for their children's achievement; and become involved in their children's schools. Programmes designed to foster linkages between families and schools have been shown to help compensate for limited family resources and effectively alter the traditional relationship between SES and school performance. This was corroborated by Flouri and Buchanman (2004) that parental involvement is a more powerful force than other family background variables such as social class, family size and level of parental education.

Parents should therefore devise means by which they would be involved in the academic activities of their children. Both parents and families should monitor and get involved in their children's academic work. The supply of school needs alone is inadequate for academic advancement and character building.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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